

ELIXIR User Journeys

Resources used in the user journeys

BioImage Archive

The [BioImage Archive](#) is a free, publicly available online resource that stores and distributes biological images.

bio.tools

[bio.tools](#) is a community-driven registry of bioinformatics software and data resources. It provides detailed information about software tools, databases, analysis workflows, and services that are used in bioinformatics and the life sciences.

DSW

[Data Stewardship Wizard](#) is an open-source platform for collaborative and living data management plans trusted worldwide — from data management pioneers to international research institutes.

FAIR Cookbook

[FAIR Cookbook](#) is a collection of birds-eye view recipes on the FAIR components, the infrastructure needed, and a set of applied examples in the Life Sciences, offering a deep dive in technical aspects of FAIR data management.

FAIRsharing

[FAIRsharing](#) is a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies.

RDMkit

The [ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit](#) has been designed to guide life scientists in their efforts to better manage their research data following the FAIR Principles.

TeSS

[Training eSupport System](#) is a one-stop shop for trainers and trainees to discover all types of resources at all levels for leveraging computational resources in the life sciences.

Contents

User Journeys	4
User Journey 1	
Q: How do I start with data management?	4
User Journey 2	
Q: How do I write a Data Management Plan?	5
User Journey 3	
Q: How do I determine if my human data is sensitive?	6
User Journey 4	
Q:How can I find relevant metadata standards for FAIR metadata handling?.....	7
User Journey 5	
Q: How do I get guidance on how to deposit high-throughput data into EBI BioImage	8
User Journey 6	
Q: As a trainer, what existing data management resources can I explore to create teaching material on DMPs?	9
FAQs	10
General data management & DMPs	10
Finding, using, sharing & storing data	11
Metadata & documentation.....	12
FAIR-related questions	13
Contributors	14

User Journeys

User Journey 1

Q: How do I start with data management?

Users:

Starting with research data management can look like an overwhelming task, but there are tools and personal expertise in place to guide and support you. This user journey is going to showcase the basic steps, supporting tools, and guidance to get started with data management:

The place to start is general guidance on data management topics, including domain-specific and task-oriented topics available at RDMkit. It is an online portal providing best practice guidelines for data management, organised along several axes, including task, domain and user role.

The first step is to identify the guidelines relevant to your case on the RDMkit. From there, the RDMkit links you to step-by-step practical instructions in the FAIR Cookbook to help you accomplish

your task. You can also find extended information and related resources about the standards in FAIRsharing, linked via both the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook.

On each RDMkit page, you can also find a link to TeSS, a website where you can find training materials and courses relevant to your needs. TeSS, as well as RDMkit, also provides links to the catalogue of computational tools for life sciences: bio.tools

User Journey 2

Q: How do I write a Data Management Plan?

Users:

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is used to structure and plan data management activities in your project. It comprises handling of data during and after the project. Many funding agencies have now made it compulsory to provide a data management plan with grant applications.

To start, we recommend you consult the [DMP page on RDMkit](#) to get an overview of what a DMP entails. In addition, on the [National pages on RDMkit](#), you can find the detailed requirements for certain funders and institutions.

Next, from the RDMkit, you can choose a tool like the DSW to create a DMP. The DSW is a questionnaire-style tool for creating, updating, and sharing your DMP. For the creation of the DMP, you may want to choose a local DSW from the [National](#)

[Resources table](#) on the RDMkit or the [DSW Cloud for ELIXIR](#). DSW also cross links with RDMkit's guidelines, should you need them when answering questions. Also, DSW imports information from FAIRsharing to help you choose among repositories, standards and policies for your project.

For further guidance, you can navigate from the RDMkit to TeSS to discover DMP-, DSW- and FAIRsharing-related training materials and events.

User Journey 3

Q: How do I determine if my human data is sensitive?

Users:

The [Data Sensitivity page](#) on the RDMkit will give you an overview of sensitive personal human data and general guidance. Then, navigate to the [Data Protection page](#) to find out how to protect sensitive data from an ethical and legal standpoint.

At this stage, it is important to review local regulations and policies for your country, which you can read about in the [National Resources pages](#) on the RDMkit. Please note that most of these are introductory resources, and we always advise seeking assistance from your Data Protection Officer (DPO) or data stewards with particular expertise in human data due to the complexity of the domain.

For a more technical perspective, follow the link from the RDMkit Data Protection page to the [FAIR Cookbook recipe](#) to learn how to represent data use conditions for sensitive data using controlled vocabularies encoded into a machine-readable metadata format.

User Journey 4

Q:How can I find relevant metadata standards for FAIR metadata handling?

Users:

The [Documentation and Metadata page](#) on the RDMkit will help you understand what you need to consider when managing the metadata for your project. To further explore the standards used in your domain as well as their connections, a link to FAIRsharing is provided.

Several relevant FAIR Cookbook recipes are linked from RDMkit that can help with the task. For example, you can follow instructions to [Create a data dictionary](#) as a FAIRCookbook recipe to define the metadata variables you need to capture. This recipe is accessible to most researchers and does

not require a great level of technical knowledge.

If you want to go further, check out the FAIR Cookbook recipe on [How to use ontologies](#) to describe your variables and values - this recipe requires some understanding of what ontologies are and how to use them. If you want to go beyond metadata standards and data dictionaries, a further recipe guides you through [Creating a metadata profile](#) from scratch if no existing standard fully meets your needs. The FAIR Cookbook recipes also link you back to RDMkit for a broader context.

User Journey 5

Q: How do I get guidance on how to deposit high-throughput data into EBI BioImage

Users:

*Anyone who wants to submit data to the BioImage Archive

Start by checking the BioImage Archive website. Follow their [online tutorial about submitting data](#) to the BioImage Archive.

If you need additional practical guidance, search the FAIR Cookbook for templates and scripts that can help with submission to BioImage Archive, such as this example on [High-Content Screening data deposition](#).

From the “What to read next?” section on the FAIR Cookbook, you can access the RDMkit [Bioimaging Data page](#), which provides general information and solutions for managing and submitting bioimaging data. The RDMkit Tool assembly section might pro-

vide insights on tooling for managing bioimaging data, such as the [OMERO Tool Assembly page](#).

Under “More information” in RDMkit, you can follow the link to the registry of training events and materials, TeSS, related to BioImage Archive, such as this hands-on tutorial on [Recommended meta-data guidelines for bioimaging data](#). You can use TeSS to find additional training by searching keywords of your choice (e.g. REMBI).

User Journey 6

Q: As a trainer, what existing data management resources can I explore to create teaching material on DMPs?

Users:

Data management guidance for trainers is available on RDMkit. For general information, guidelines and best practices about DMP read the RDMkit page "[Data Management Plan](#)". The DSW is one tool that facilitates management planning using a systematic, questionnaire-based approach. To shape the experience of your training audience, you might consider setting up a [dedicated instance of DSW](#) to customise different aspects. You might want to consult your local IT administrative team regarding IT security issues.

An equally important aspect of creating a DMP is to be familiar with institutional guidelines, which can be learned about via the [National Resources page](#) available on RDMkit.

You may explore how existing course materials address the topic of Data Management Planning, e.g. through hands-on sessions, in the form of webinar, or a mix of theoretical and practical content. Following the link from RDMkit, you can go to TeSS to find training materials and events. Use the keyword "data management plan". Further, you may look for "train the trainers" on TeSS to get information on events and workshop materials to improve your training skills.

FAQs

General data management & DMPs

How do I find standards for data and datasets to add to the DMP?

RDMkit contains knowledge on [general considerations on standards on metadata and documentation](#). You can find additional standards on RDMkit [pages specific to your domain](#).

Moreover, [FAIRsharing](#) provides a curated list of data formats and metadata standards. To add to the DMP, DSW provides integration that allows searching for a standard from FAIRsharing directly via the DSW interface; then, the standard record is linked within the DMP.

How can I calculate the costs for RDM?

An [RDMkit page on RDM costs](#) explains the different aspects to consider when estimating them. The [DSW Storage Costs Evaluator](#) (based on this [calculation model](#)) is a more detailed tool for evaluating data storage costs.

How do I meet the DM requirements from my funder?

Check the [RDMkit national pages](#) for recommendations from national funders. If your national funder is not mentioned on the national page, contact the page coordinator.

You can find further guidance on the [Data Management Planning task page](#):

Consult the documentation of your funding agency or institution, or contact them to figure out if they require or recommend a DMP template.

A core DMP template has been provided by [Science Europe](#).

Read the DMP guidelines in the [Horizon Europe](#)

[Programme Guide](#) and the [Horizon Europe Annotated Model Grant Agreement](#). The Horizon Europe DMP template can be downloaded from the [Reference Documents](#) page by clicking on “Templates & forms,” “Project reporting templates,” and then on “Data management plan (HE).”

If you provide services on data management planning to other people, you might want to consider adopting the DMP [Common Standard](#) model from the Research Data Alliance to produce a machine-actionable DMP template.

To what extent do I need separate DMPs for different research outputs? How to navigate generic vs specific?

The answer to this question depends highly on the project’s or funder’s exact DMP requirements [RDMkit Planning page](#) provides some further guidance.

Where do I find guidance to write DMP for software mainly?

When it comes to finding guidance on writing a Data Management Plan (DMP) for software (actually you probably are asking about software management planning - SMP), ELIXIR Europe provides a range of resources that can be of great assistance:

1. Software [Best Practices Group \(4OSS\)](#): ELIXIR’s Software Best Practices Group, also known as 4OSS (Open Source Software), is a community-driven initiative aimed at promoting and advancing best practices in software development across the life sciences. The group offers guidance, resources, and tools for developing high-quality software, which can be incorporated into your DMP to ensure the software’s long-term sustainability and usability.
2. [ELIXIR Software Management Plan \(SMP\)](#): The ELIXIR SMP is a comprehensive guide specifically designed to assist researchers in managing their software projects effectively. It provides detailed information on various aspects

of software development, including version control, documentation, licensing, and sustainability. The SMP can be valuable when crafting your DMP for software.

Software Management Wizard: It is an interactive online tool designed to help researchers navigate the process of managing software projects. It provides step-by-step guidance and generates customized recommendations based on your specific project requirements. The Software Management Wizard can assist you in identifying the key elements to include in your DMP for software and ensure compliance with best practices.

Finding, using, sharing & storing data

How can I decide which data I can delete? How long do I need to keep my data for, after the end of a grant?

For general guidance on data preservation, take a look at [Data Preservation page on RDMkit](#). Data preservation strategies should be covered in [your project's Data Management Plan](#). Your institution, funder or [country](#) may also have additional rules you need to follow. If there is a Data Stewardship Wizard instance available in your country or institution, this may be a good source of information.

Where can I look for existing datasets?

One way to start is to find the repository that is usually used for deposition of the type of data using the [EBI Data submissions wizard](#) and search directly there.

[RDMkit Existing Data page](#) contains more considerations and solutions to find datasets/databases like registries, indices and search engines. If you are searching for datasets linked to specific articles [Europe PMC](#) provides you with specific search functions for this.

FAIRSharing.org is a registry of standards and data-

bases which can help you to find relevant repositories - you can learn more about it [here](#).

How can I share my data with my collaborators in a safe and secure way?

Before sharing any data, consider the type of data you are sharing and the legal and ethical implications.

There are [guidelines](#) available in the RDMkit (Data Lifecycle [?](#) Sharing) providing recommendations for different levels of sharing. The FAIR Cookbook has [several recipes](#) covering the practicalities of data sharing, such as [sharing via SFTP](#).

How to submit/deposit my data to a repository to obtain a persistent identifier or accession to mention in my publication?

Identify the most appropriate hosting solution for your data early on in your project. The RDMkit has some [general guidance on picking the right repository](#) as well as a link to the full [list of ELIXIR deposition databases](#). [The RDMkit Domain pages](#) list resources appropriate for each domain.

Public repositories normally have specific submission guidelines, and you should review these to ensure that you build any special consideration such as metadata requirements into your data collection process.

Besides those, there are also generic resources such as [Zenodo](#) where data can be deposited. Examples of how to submit to specific repositories are available in the FAIR Cookbook: [FCB009](#) and [FCB045](#)

FAIRsharing helps you to [find the right database for your data type](#), including descriptions and links on how to submit data. It also provides [educational material on databases](#) in PDF form. There is a [FAIRsharing Assistant](#) to help guide you through FAIRsharing.

I think my dataset is anonymous as I removed all personal information (name, surname etc.). Why do GDPR measures apply to my dataset?

Removing personal data does not guarantee that your dataset is truly anonymised, as discussed in [data sensitivity page in the RDMkit](#). The RDMkit has guidance on [How to protect data under GDPR](#). In addition to consulting these resources, talk to your node or institution's data stewardship team for guidance that takes into account any national legislation you need to be aware of.

How do I know if my non-human data is sensitive?

Some types of non-human data, such as biodiversity data, may still qualify as "sensitive". Take a look at the [RDMkit page on data sensitivity](#) for more information.

What is the FAIR way to deposit/attach data, used in my research for a publication?

Do not be tempted to attach data as supplementary materials - deposit the data in a repository that is as open as possible and as closed as necessary! RDMkit provides [guidance on how to pick the most appropriate repository](#) for your domain.

FAIRsharing helps you search the databases in your domain, and the [FAIRsharing Assistant](#) can guide you through this process. You can also search FAIRsharing for the data policy of the journal you are targeting to see what requirements they have.

Metadata & documentation

What minimum metadata should I use?

Every field will have its own specific metadata needs.

To get an idea on your field specific requirements, you can consult [RDMkit](#) and select "[your domain](#)". The "your domain" will give you an overview of where you can deposit your data, how your metadata should be structured, which tools can be used for this etc.

Repository specific: go to the database you want to deposit your data in and check their metadata requirements. Even within the same field, there might be small differences.

[There is a study that compared all available metadata schemes.](#)

[FAIRsharing](#) provides a registry for databases and the respective connected minimal metadata standards.

I have metadata in a README.md in a project folder. Is it enough? What is a better way to keep metadata?

In short: it is a good start, but not enough. - You can find ways to improve this by reading the following pages on RDMkit:

[Documentation and Metadata](#) provides a starting point

The [Machine actionability](#) page provides more in depth concepts

[Collecting and processing the metadata and data](#), provides solutions and file formats that can be used for collecting metadata

What software can I use to document data?

There is no specific software for documenting data. RDMkit provides some suggestions in its [guidance on capturing/documenting the data](#). The page also discusses [adding appropriate metadata](#).

I am not able to code, how do I apply ontologies in my daily research?

You don't have to code to use ontologies. Check

if there are recommended ontologies that you should use and your purpose of using ontologies, [as described in RDMkit](#). One way to identify which ontology should be used is by checking the domain specific standards in FAIRsharing, for example by using the [FAIRsharing Assistant](#).

How can I get a persistent identifier for my software or website?

The [RDMkit provides a consideration on different types of persistent identifiers](#).

For software, the easiest solution is to generate a persistent [identifier for your Github repository through Zenodo](#).

For web resources, you can review the FAIR Cookbook recipe [for creating resolvable identifiers](#).

FAIR-related questions

How do I evaluate FAIRness of data/software?

RDMkit provides [lightweight guidance](#) on assessing the wider context of data management capabilities. For specific tools related to data assessments, start with the [FAIR Evaluator tool](#) (Recipe 1 in the [Fair Cookbook](#)) or the [indicators](#) on the [FAIR Data Maturity](#) website to locate yourself on the FAIR maturity spectrum. Then, follow additional recipes from the FAIR Cookbook to move up the maturity ladder. For assessing software, take a look at [FAIR Evaluator](#) and the [Software Management Wizard](#).

Additional resources can be found on [FAIRsharing.org](#) or [FAIRassist](#), [Bio.tools](#) and [OpenEBench/tools](#) list several tools and services dealing with FAIR evaluation of resources.

How do I make sure that the data is FAIR and also queryable? Do I have to create something of my own (like a dashboard where data is queryable using an SQL database) or is there something ready to use?

Submit Data to a Public repository

- As a starting point to make your data FAIR we recommend that you deposit your data in a trustworthy public repository, such as the ELIXIR Recommended [Deposition Databases](#).
- You can use the FAIR Cookbook recipe [Registering your dataset in Wikidata](#) to deposit your data to a relevant repository
- Find further materials based on the domain your data corresponds to at the [RDMkit “Your domain”](#).
- If none of the existing approaches work for you, you can find more information on how to [build a catalogue of datasets](#)

Metadata

Add appropriate and adequate metadata to your dataset as advised in the RDMkit [Documentation and Metadata page](#).

ELIXIR FAIR assessment resources

Based on the nature of your data (e.g. bioinformatic tools, datasets, etc.) and execution type (i.e. manual or automatic), find your FAIRness assessment service within [FAIRassist’s extensive list](#). Some recommendations are:

- [FAIR Evaluator tool](#)
- [Data Maturity Model](#)

Training resources on the introductions to FAIR principles

- “Introduction to FAIR principles - Open science through FAIR health data networks: dream or reality?” ([TeSS](#))
- “Practically FAIR” ([TeSS](#))
- “FAIRplus fellowship programme” ([TeSS](#))
- Data sharing ([RDMkit](#))

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